

RATE-DEPENDENT BEHAVIOR OF ARAMID FIBERS COATED WITH SHEAR THICKENING FLUIDS

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ABSTRACT

Due to their high strength and stiffness and in particular toughness, aramid fabrics have been used in bulletproof applications. Recently, aramid fabrics have been coated with shear thickening fluid (STF), demonstrating more enhanced bulletproof and mechanical properties. In our previous study, the shear thickening behavior of STF-coated aramid fabrics were characterized using picture-frame and bias extension tests, revealing that the STF effect was in fact observed over yarn crossovers at mesoscale. This observation can explain improved bulletproof and mechanical properties due to STF, however it is still unclear at microscale level, i.e., whether STF-coated single aramid fiber inside yarns can contribute to the STF effect of STF-coated aramid fabrics. This study aimed to investigate the rate-dependent behavior of STF-coated single aramid fiber inside aramid yarns. A STF was prepared by making the colloidal suspension of silica nano particles (about 84 nm in size) in poly (ethylene glycol). The STF was then coated onto a single aramid fiber and aramid yarns. A special test rig was using 3D printers that can hold the single aramid fiber passing through the aramid yarns, in which it contacts with many other aramid fibers. The test rig was installed into a universal tensile machine, measuring the force that the single fiber experienced.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aramid fabrics have been used in various fields such as aerospace, automotive and military, because of their high strength and stiffness and in particular toughness. Especially, aramid fabrics have been widely used in bulletproof field due to their high mechanical properties and mobility [1-3].

Shear thickening fluid (STF) is a non-Newtonian fluid featuring the increasing viscosity at high strain rate applied. Shear thickening behaviour is induced by nano-clustering during shear deformation of concentrated suspension. STF is prepared by making the colloidal suspension of solid particles in a liquid. Accordingly, the fluidic behaviour of STF can be tailored by the particle size, shape and concentration. STF is also characterised by an increase in viscosity when the shear rate increases past a critical value. Though STF is much less common than shear thinning materials in industrial field, it can be used in bulletproof field and expected to enhance bulletproof efficiency owing to their improved mechanical properties at high shear rate [6]. Recently, STF-treated aramid fabrics have been researched to enhance the bulletproof efficiency maintaining the lightweight. STF-treated aramid fabrics demonstrated high stab-resistance and decreased penetration depth because STF depressed the shear deformation on fabrics and dispersed the impacts effectively through the fabrics.

In a previous study, the shear thickening behavior of STF-treated aramid fabrics was characterized using picture-frame and bias extension tests at macroscale [5]. This observation can explain improved bulletproof and mechanical properties due to STF, however it is still unclear at microscale level, whether STF-coated single aramid fibers inside yarns can contribute to the STF effect of STF-coated aramid fabrics. Therefore, the object of this study was to investigate the rate-dependent behavior of STF-coated single aramid fiber inside aramid yarns.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Shear thickening fluid (STF) and aramid fibers

STF was made of silica nano-particles and PEG (MW 200). PEG was used as a dispersant in this study because it was less volatile at low temperature and could minimize the aging. Silica particles were supplied in the sol form in methanol. The proportion and size of averaged silica particles were 30 wt% and 84 nm, respectively. The solution was mixed with PEG, making the proportion of silica particle 65 wt% after evaporating methanol (i.e., PEG 35wt% and silica particle 65wt%, independent of methanol). After hand mixing for 5 m, the solution was mixed again using sonication for 5 m. Methanol was evaporated in room temperature condition over 12 hours.

Aramid fabrics used in this study were HT840 (Heracron, KOLON). The number of filaments in a yarn of the fabrics was about 666. The diameter of the filament and the yarn was 11 μm and 0.4 mm, respectively. The STF was coated onto a single aramid fiber and aramid yarns.

2.2 Characterization

The rheological data of STF was experimentally obtained using a stress-controlled rheometer (AR 2000, TA Instruments) in steady-shear rate sweep mode at room temperature (from 1 to 10^4s^{-1}). A cone (with 1° angle and 20mm diameter) and plate tool were used in this test

Single fiber pull-out test was carried out. A special testing rig was designed and fabricated using a 3D printer to hold the single aramid fiber passing through the aramid yarns contacting many other aramid fibers. The shear rate was controlled by the head speed of the testing machine (Universal Tensile Machine, R&B Corp.) ranging from 1 to 500 mm/min.

2.3 Single fiber shear test

To calculate shear stress and shear rate of a single aramid fiber passing the aramid yarns, the intercept length of a single fiber was calculated. A statistical approach was used here. The length of the intercept line depends only on the distance from the sphere's center, marked e in the figure 1 [4].

Figure 1: A line passing through a sphere.

When all the intercept lines pass through the sphere, the fraction of all intercept lines can be calculated as a function of length. According to a result obtained by Monte-Carlo methods, the probability distribution curve for intercept lengths through a sphere is straight line as shown in figure 2. When calculating the mean intercept length by statistics, the mean intercept length calculated by statistics was $2/3$ times the diameter of the sphere.

Figure 2: Frequency distribution for intercept lengths through a sphere of radius D.

At single aramid fiber pull-out test, the shear strain and shear rate were defined as in figure 3. The velocity (V) was already known as the head speed and the force (F) was also known as the result of pull-out test. However, the separation height (H) and the area (A) should be calculated by some assumptions. When the separation height and the area were calculated, the shear stress and the strain rate could be also calculated. The shear stress and strain rate are given by the following equation (1).

$$\text{Shear stress } \tau = \frac{F}{A} \quad \text{Strain rate } \dot{\gamma} = \frac{V}{H} \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of shear deformation

For calculating the separation height (H), it was assumed that only 1 layer subjected to the pulled-out filament is related to shear deformation. Therefore, separation height (H) is equal to the diameter of the cross-section of filament (11 μm). The area ($A = 2\pi rl$) was calculated by the contacted area using the radius of a fiber (r) and the mean intercept length (l). *Through the test, the following shear rates were imposed.*

Table 1: The shear rate imposed on a single fiber by the head speed

The head speed (mm/min)	1	10	20	50	100	300	500
Shear rate (s^{-1})	1.52	15.15	30.30	75.76	151.52	454.55	757.58

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In viscosity measurement, the representative curve of the viscosity of the prepared STF (silica 65 wt%) and the shear stress of the STF were obtained as shown in figure 4. The shear thickening phenomenon was observed over the critical shear rate (about $720s^{-1}$). The shear stress increased by increasing the shear rate.

Figure 4: The viscosity (left) and the shear stress (right) of STF (silica 65 wt%)

In neat single fiber pull-out test, the shear stress was not changed as the shear rate increased as shown in figure 5. In other words, the rate-dependent behavior was not observed in the neat single fiber.

Figure 5: The shear stress of neat single fiber

On the other hand, in STF-coated single fiber pull-out test, the shear stress increased by increasing the shear rate, demonstrating the rate-dependent behavior of STF-coated single fiber (see figure 6). We believe that this was caused by the STF effects of single fiber on the shear stress during the fiber pull-

out test. More systematic study is in progress and will be presented at the Conference.

Figure 6: The shear stress of STF-coated single fiber

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the shear stress of STF-coated single aramid fiber was evaluated by single fiber pull-out test. In neat single aramid fiber, the rate-dependent behaviour was not observed. The shear stress of STF-coated single fiber increased by increasing the shear rate, exhibiting the rate-dependent behaviour, which can be ascribed to the the STF effects of single fiber at microscale level.

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